

Manganese (II) Complexes of Tetradentate Schiff Bases

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Preparation and properties of some Mn(II) complexes of dibasic, tetradentate Schiff bases are described. The magnetic properties of these complexes are somewhat lower than the spin-only value for a d^5 system and these lower magnetic moment values are discussed in terms of possible structures for these compounds. The magnetic properties of the aerial oxidation product of Mn(SB), where SBH₂ is a molecule of Schiff base derived from 1,3-diaminopropane-2-ol and salicylaldehyde, are reported.

For the last few years we have been studying the metallic complexes of Schiff bases¹⁻⁸. Preliminary studies on the manganese (II) complexes of tetradentate Schiff bases are reported in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

The Schiff bases were prepared as previously described⁵, and the following abbreviations were used :

- (a) SBH₂ = Schiff base derived from 1,3-diaminopropane-2-ol and salicylaldehyde,
- (b) SB'H₂ = Schiff base derived from 1, 3-diaminopropane-2-ol and 3-aldehydosalicylic acid, and
- (c) SB''H₂ = Schiff base derived from 1, 3-diaminopropane-2-ol and acetylacetone.

Preparation of the complexes : Mn(SB) : This compound was prepared by refluxing (2 hrs.) together stoichiometric amounts of manganous acetate tetrahydrate and the Schiff base in ethanol. The green complex obtained on cooling, was filtered and then recrystallized from minimum volume of ethanol, filtered and dried in vacuum desiccator over anhydrous calcium chloride.

Mn(SB') : The stoichiometric amounts of manganous acetate tetrahydrate in ethanol and the Schiff base in 5% aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide was refluxed together (2 hrs.) and the precipitated greenish yellow compound was filtered off and washed with alcohol and dried in vacuum desiccator over anhydrous calcium chloride.

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Mn(SB''): On refluxing (2 hrs.) stoichiometric quantities of manganous acetate tetrahydrate and the Schiff base in ethanol a chocolate coloured solution was obtained, which was evaporated to dryness on water-bath. The brown mass, thus obtained, was extracted with ether, which on standing in the refrigerator for 2 days gave brown crystals. This was filtered off and recrystallized from minimum volume of ether, filtered and dried in vacuum desiccator over anhydrous calcium chloride.

TABLE

Elemental analyses^a, and magnetic moments^b of Mn(II)—Schiff base complexes

Complex	C (%)		H (%)		N (%)		Mn (%)		μ_{eff} BM (Temp.)	Reference
	Cald.	Found	Cald.	Found	Cald.	Found	Cald.	Found		
1. Mn(SB)	58.12	58.00	4.55	4.51	7.98	8.13	15.65	15.65	5.40 (296°K)	Present study
2. Mn(SB')	51.93	52.22	3.64	3.58	6.38	6.17	12.51	12.82	5.19 (302°K)	„
3. Mn(SB'')	50.82	50.67	6.51	6.30	9.12	9.00	17.89	17.72	5.67 (302°K)	„
4. Mn(ASA-en) ^c	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	5.88 (303°K)	2 ^g
5. Mn(ASA-O-phen) ^d	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	5.47 (303°K)	2 ^g
6. Mn(Salen) ^e	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	5.27 (300°K)	9 ^g
7. Mn(HA-en) ^f	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	5.32 (295°K)	10 ^g

(a) (%) of C, H, and N were analyzed by Alfred Bernhardt Microanalytical Laboratory, West Germany.

(b) Magnetic susceptibilities were measured as described previously^{2,5}.

(c) (ASA-en) = dianion of the Schiff base derived from 3-aldehydosalicylic acid and ethylenediamine.

(d) (ASA-O-phen) = dianion of the Schiff base derived from 3-aldehydosalicylic acid and orthophenylenediamine.

(e) Salen = NN'-ethylene bis (salicylideneiminato)-

(f) HA-en = bis (O-hydroxyacetophenone) ethylenediamine.

(g) Few magnetic moment values of similar type of Mn(II) chelates are quoted from published papers for comparison with values obtained in the present study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The manganese(II) complexes under study are of the type [Mn(L)], where LH₂ = a molecule of the dibasic, tetradentate Schiff base and the room temperature magnetic moments are in the range 5.19 to 5.67 BM (Table). The compounds are stable when dried, but in the wet condition, the compounds darkened, possibly due to aerial oxidation. The magnetic moment (after the aerial oxidation) of wet [Mn(SB)] was found to be 3.62 B.M. at 303°K and the elemental analysis roughly corresponds to Mn(SB)(OH).H₂O (Found : N, 7.53; calod. N, 7.22%, consistent result for the percentage of manganese could not be obtained). It is insoluble in many organic solvents, which precludes the molecular weight determination.

The magnetic moments of the Mn (II) chelates under study (Table) are less than that generally observed for spin-free d^5 system. Many manganese (II) complexes of dibasic, tetradentate Schiff bases have been reported earlier, which shows this type of lower magnetic moments (Table). This has been explained^{9,11,12} with the help of antiferromagnetic exchange interaction between the manganese ions in the solids. The lower magnetic moments of the present manganese (II) complexes may be either due to the presence of antiferromagnetic interaction between the manganese atoms in the solid state, or, due to aerial oxidation of Mn (II) \rightarrow Mn (III) during the preparation of the compounds. In the absence of magnetic susceptibility data over a temperature range nothing can be said definitely about the presence of anti-ferromagnetic interactions.

As regards the isolation of Mn(SB)(OH).H₂O, no reproducible results were obtained, and therefore, we defer to comment on this particular compound. However, it may be mentioned that similar insoluble, polymeric compounds were isolated by aerial oxidation of wet Mn(Salen) and their structures were discussed in terms of a binuclear (Salen) Mn-O-Mn (Salen).H₂O. However, without a more detailed investigation it is not possible to ascertain the reasons for this lower magnetic moments of the present manganese (II) complexes. Further work on these complexes is in progress.

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